

1. Evaluation area (Viewpoints & Measurement levels): [HIGH]

Pre-requisite:

- Measurement levels
- Generalization of the viewpoints (Sponsor, Coordinator, Implementer)
- Scoping using the “Measurement Level-Viewpoint Matrix”

Do you think that the evaluation area represents clearly WHO is interested in the evaluation and WHICH measurable entities need to be considered?

- Does it create the appropriate mindset for the evaluation?
- Generalization of viewpoints realistic?

2. Primary / complementary measures: [HIGH]

Pre-requisite:

- Primary and complementary
- Iron triangle metaphor
- Categories (Bonus Q)

[Give example of code inspection to further explain the iron triangle]

Do you think that the consideration of primary and complementary measures increases the accuracy for improvement evaluation?

Does it provide a more complete view on the effects of the initiative?

Do you think that the derivation of complementary measures (based on the principle of the iron triangle) clarifies WHAT should be measured and it should be measured?

Bonus question:

From the categories of measurement for each level, do you think that the categories in all levels are complete? Are there any categories which are not included?

3. Derivation of measure for improvement evaluation: [HIGH]

Pre-requisite:

- Derivation of metrics using the evaluation area + primary/complementary measures using GQM.

[Show example and connect to the previous concepts of evaluation area and primary/complementary measures]

Do you think that the proposed approach provides a clear and systematic method for the elicitation of measures of improvement evaluation?

- Interface SPI-MEF ↔ GQM appropriate?
- Useful in practice?
- Do you have other opinion?

4. Time to evaluate (Periodic evaluation): [HIGH]

Pre-requisite:

- Lag factor
- Degradation factor
- Periodic evaluation

Do you think that the determination of the appropriate time to evaluate using the concept of Lag Factor and Degradation Factor is sound?

- Determination of concrete LF/DF

Do you think that periodic evaluation (to see the trend over time) is an effective way to gauge the outcome of SPI initiatives?

- Is it an overhead?
- Doable in reality?
- Periodic evaluation more accurate?

5. Holistic View: **HIGH**

Pre-requisite:

- Present the idea of “holistic view” in a radar chart.
- Consolidation / calculation of multiple evaluation results into “one representative value”

Do you think that the proposed model to construct the “Holistic View” is sound?

- ...by considering Measurement Levels and Viewpoints in the model
- Feasible in practice in terms of its usefulness and cost effectiveness?

Can you identify any improvement opportunity for the model?

6. Opportunity matrix: [MODERATE]

Pre-requisite:

- Present the opportunity matrix and highlight the following:
 - Accuracy → Primary/complementary measures + Cross-examination + Confounding factors
 - Coverage → “Onion” + Viewpoint

From your experience, is increasing accuracy and coverage the appropriate way to improve the quality of evaluation?

- To which extent will confounding factors affect the validity of the evaluation results?
- Is the categorization of accuracy and coverage sound?
- Which are the most critical payoffs you can think of when trying to achieve a high quality evaluation according to the opportunity matrix proposed in SPI-MEF?
- What is, in your opinion, more important for a high quality evaluation?
 - Accuracy – Why?
 - Coverage – Why?

7. Applicability: [HIGH]

To which extent do you consider the idea that the evaluation of improvement is independent from the actual initiative as realistic?

- ...independent from e.g. frameworks (CMM, SPICE, etc.), practices and tools

Do you think that the framework scales with increasing complexity of the SPI initiative?

- i.e. with the number of introduced process changes

To what extent do you think SPI-MEF is applicable in different company settings (size, core business, culture)?

8. Suggestions: [HIGH]

Can you name and explain any deficiency you have observed in the framework?

Can you name and explain the major benefits you have observed in the framework?

Do you have any suggestions to improve SPI-MEF in terms of applicability, realism or usefulness?